

Supplementary Material: Compiling Defeasible Inference: A Dynamic Approach to System Z

1 Supplementary Material A: Algorithms

Algorithm 1 BaseRank

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1: Input:  $\mathcal{K} = (\Gamma, \Delta)$ 
2: Output:  $Z_{\mathcal{K}} = (\Delta_0, \dots, \Delta_{k-1}, \Delta_{\infty})$ 
3:  $i \leftarrow 0$ 
4:  $E_i = \{\alpha \rightarrow \beta \mid \alpha \sim \beta \in \Delta\}$ 
5: while  $E_i \neq E_{i-1}$  do
6:    $E_{i+1} \leftarrow \{\alpha \rightarrow \beta \in E_i \mid \Gamma \cup E_i \models \neg\alpha\}$ 
7:    $\Delta_i \leftarrow E_i \setminus E_{i+1}$ 
8:    $i \leftarrow i + 1$ 
9:  $\Delta_{\infty} \leftarrow E_{i-1}$ 
10: if  $E_{i-1} = \emptyset$  then
11:    $k \leftarrow i - 1$ 
12: else
13:    $k \leftarrow i$ 
14: return  $(\Delta_0, \dots, \Delta_{k-1}, \Delta_{\infty})$ 

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BaseRank. BaseRank computes the Z-partitioning by repeatedly peeling off all defaults that are *tolerated* by the current remainder Casini, Meyer, and Varzinczak (2019). At iteration i , let E_i be the set of materializations $\alpha \rightarrow \beta$ of the remaining defaults. We form $\Gamma \cup E_i$ and move to the next remainder E_{i+1} all rules whose antecedent α is *incompatible* with this theory (i.e., $\Gamma \cup E_i \models \neg\alpha$); the rules that stay form the i -th Z-layer Δ_i . Intuitively, Δ_i contains the “most generally applicable” defaults among those left, because their antecedents still have models once the current remainder is assumed. The loop stops when the remainder stabilizes; the residual set is Δ_{∞} . This procedure is equivalent to Pearl’s tolerance test and yields the unique Z-partitioning. Its cost is driven by the number of entailment checks (at most $|\Delta|^2$ in the worst case).

RationalClosure. RationalClosure answers a query $r = (\alpha \sim \beta)$ from a Z-partitioning by searching for the least rank at which α is consistent Casini, Meyer, and Varzinczak (2019). Starting from the most specific theory (obtained by materializing all remaining layers), it iteratively drops the current lowest finite layer until $\Gamma \cup \bigcup_{j \geq i} \Delta_j \not\models \neg\alpha$

Algorithm 2 RationalClosure

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1: Input:  $Z_{\mathcal{K}} = (\Delta_0, \dots, \Delta_{k-1}, \Delta_{\infty}), \Gamma, \alpha \sim \beta$ 
2: Output: true if inference, otherwise false
3:  $i \leftarrow 0$ 
4:  $\Delta = \bigcup_{j \geq i} \Delta_j$ 
5: while  $\Gamma \cup \Delta \models \neg\alpha$  and  $\Delta \neq \emptyset$  do
6:    $\Delta \leftarrow \Delta \setminus \Delta_i$ 
7:    $i \leftarrow i + 1$ 
8: return  $\Delta \cup \Gamma \models \alpha \rightarrow \beta$ 

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or no layers remain. If no α -worlds exist, r is accepted vacuously. Otherwise, r holds iff $\Gamma \cup \bigcup_{j \geq i} \Delta_j \models \alpha \rightarrow \beta$, i.e., at the minimal rank where α can be true, no world falsifies β . Operationally this separates the consistency search (where does α start being possible?) from the preference test (among those worlds, do any violate β ?). The procedure matches System Z semantics and runs in at most $|\Delta|$ entailment tests.

2 Supplementary Material B: Theorem Proofs

Theorem 1. *The time complexity of the Preprocess algorithm is bounded by*

$$\mathcal{O}\left((|\Gamma| + m \cdot \max_{r \in \Delta} |r[0]|) \cdot \prod_{j=0}^{m-1} \max_{r \in \Delta} |r[1]|\right),$$

and requires exponential time in the worst case.

Proof. Let $M_0 = \max_{r \in \Delta} |r[0]|$ and $M_1 = \max_{r \in \Delta} |r[1]|$, and let $s = |E_i| \leq m$ denote the number of conditionals processed at iteration i .

Line 6. The algorithm conjoins the ROBDD materializations of all conditionals in E_i and then conjoins the result with Γ . Folding conjunction with apply over s operands and using that each apply call runs in $\mathcal{O}(|G_1| \cdot |G_2|)$ time Bryant (1986), we obtain the bound

$$\mathcal{O}\left(|\Gamma| \cdot \prod_{\ell=0}^{s-1} M_1\right).$$

(Each materialization has size at most M_1 .)

Line 7. Let H_i denote the result of line 6. For each $r \in E_i$ the algorithm performs one conjunction $H_i \cdot r[0]$, which costs

$$O(|H_i| \cdot |r[0]|) \leq O\left(|\Gamma| \cdot \prod_{\ell=0}^{s-1} M_1\right) \cdot M_0.$$

Summing over the s antecedents gives

$$O\left(s \cdot M_0 \cdot |\Gamma| \cdot \prod_{\ell=0}^{s-1} M_1\right).$$

Taking the worst iteration ($s = m$) and adding the contributions of lines 6 and 7 yields

$$O\left(|\Gamma| + m \cdot M_0\right) \cdot \prod_{j=0}^{m-1} M_1,$$

which matches the stated bound. Finally, unbounded conjunction over a growing number of ROBDD operands can cause exponential blow-up in the worst case (see, e.g., Darwiche and Marquis (2002)). Since line 6 conjoins up to m materializations, the algorithm is exponential in the worst case. \square

Theorem 2. *Preprocess is sound/complete for computing $\Gamma_{\mathcal{K}}^Z$ and $\Delta_{\mathcal{K}}^Z$.*

Proof. Assume BaseRank is sound and complete for the Z-partitioning Casini, Meyer, and Varzinczak (2019). We show that Preprocess (i) produces the same layers, encoded as ROBDDs, and (ii) returns at each iteration the corresponding materialized theory.

Let E_i be the remainder of compiled defaults at iteration i , and let

$$R_i = \{r[1] \mid r \in E_i\}$$

be their compiled materializations. Line 6 of Preprocess constructs

$$\Gamma_i = \Gamma \cdot \prod R_i,$$

i.e. the ROBDD of the classical theory obtained by materializing all defaults in E_i on top of Γ .

In the classical BaseRank procedure, a default $r = \alpha \vdash \beta$ is tolerated by the current remainder iff

$$\Gamma \wedge \alpha \wedge \bigwedge_{\alpha' \vdash \beta' \in E_i} (\alpha' \rightarrow \beta')$$

is satisfiable. ROBDD compilation preserves (un)satisfiability, so this condition is equivalent to the ROBDD test

$$\Gamma_i \cdot r[0] \neq 0.$$

Thus the set E_{i+1} selected by Preprocess at iteration i (defaults that are not tolerated and hence remain in the remainder) coincides with the remainder that BaseRank would produce at the same step, and $\Delta_i = E_i \setminus E_{i+1}$ is exactly the i -th Z-layer.

Removing Δ_i yields E_{i+1} , and line 6 in the next iteration updates

$$\Gamma_{i+1} = \Gamma \cdot \prod R_{i+1},$$

which is precisely the materialized theory for the next remainder. By induction on i , Preprocess therefore (a) returns the ROBDD-encoded Z-partitioning $\Delta_{\mathcal{K}}^Z = (\Delta_0, \Delta_1, \dots, \Delta_\infty)$ matching BaseRank, and (b) returns the tuple of materialized theories $\Gamma_{\mathcal{K}}^Z = (\Gamma_0, \Gamma_1, \dots, \Gamma_\infty)$ computed at each iteration. Hence the procedure is sound and complete for both outputs. \square

Theorem 3. *The time complexity of the MinTheory algorithm is bounded by*

$$\mathcal{O}\left(\left(\max_j |\Gamma_j|\right) \cdot |\varphi| \cdot \log k\right),$$

and requires polynomial time in the worst case.

Proof. Let $M = \max_j |\Gamma_j|$. The algorithm performs a binary search on the index set $\{0, \dots, k-1\}$ for the least i such that $\Gamma_i \cdot \varphi \neq 0$. This is valid because the theories weaken with i (i.e., $\Gamma_i \models \Gamma_{i+1}$), hence the predicate $P(i): \Gamma_i \cdot \varphi \neq 0$ is monotone. Each iteration evaluates $P(i)$ by one conjunction $\Gamma_i \cdot \varphi$ plus a zero-test. Using Bryant's bound for apply, this costs $O(|\Gamma_i| \cdot |\varphi|) \leq O(M \cdot |\varphi|)$; the zero-test is $O(1)$ under pointer canonicity (or $O(|\Gamma_i \cdot \varphi|)$, which is dominated by the conjunction cost). Binary search performs at most $\lceil \log_2 k \rceil$ iterations, so the total time is

$$O(M \cdot |\varphi| \cdot \log k).$$

This is polynomial in the size of the inputs. \square

Theorem 4. *MinTheory is sound and complete for computing $\kappa_{\mathcal{K}}^Z(\varphi)$.*

Proof. Let $\Delta_{\mathcal{K}}^Z = (\Delta_0, \dots, \Delta_{k-1}, \Delta_\infty)$ and recall that the Z-materialisation is given by

$$\Gamma_i = \Gamma \wedge \bigwedge_{\alpha \vdash \beta \in \bigcup_{j \geq i} \Delta_j} (\alpha \beta), \quad \Gamma_i = \text{ROBDD}(\Gamma_i).$$

A standard property of System Z (used in RationalClosure) is that, for any $\omega \models \Gamma$,

$$(*) \quad \kappa_{\mathcal{K}}^Z(\omega) \leq i \iff \omega \models \Gamma_i.$$

Indeed, $\kappa_{\mathcal{K}}^Z(\omega) \leq i$ iff ω falsifies no default in $\bigcup_{j \geq i} \Delta_j$, which is equivalent to satisfying every materialisation in Γ_i .

From (*) it follows that for any formula φ

$$\kappa_{\mathcal{K}}^Z(\varphi) = \min \{i \in \{0, \dots, k-1\} \mid \Gamma_i \wedge \varphi \text{ is satisfiable}\},$$

with $\kappa_{\mathcal{K}}^Z(\varphi) = \infty$ if no such i exists. ROBDD compilation preserves (un)satisfiability, so $\Gamma_i \wedge \varphi$ is satisfiable iff $\Gamma_i \cdot \varphi \neq 0$. Hence

$$\kappa_{\mathcal{K}}^Z(\varphi) = \min \{i \in \{0, \dots, k-1\} \mid \Gamma_i \cdot \varphi \neq 0\},$$

again with the convention that the minimum is ∞ if the set is empty.

Algorithm MinTheory performs a binary search over $i \in \{0, \dots, k-1\}$ on the predicate

$$P(i) : \Gamma_i \cdot \varphi \neq 0$$

and returns the least i satisfying P , or k if none exists. By the characterization above, the returned index coincides with $\kappa_{\mathcal{K}}^Z(\varphi)$, where k is used to represent ∞ . This is exactly the consistency-search step in RationalClosure, specialised to computing the rank of φ . Hence MinTheory is sound and complete for computing $\kappa_{\mathcal{K}}^Z(\varphi)$. \square

Theorem 5. *The time complexity of the Inference algorithm is bounded by*

$$\mathcal{O}\left(\max_j |\Gamma_j| \cdot (|\mathbf{r}[0]| \cdot \log k + |\mathbf{r}[1]|)\right),$$

and requires polynomial time in the worst case.

Proof. Let $M = \max_j |\Gamma_j|$. The call $i \leftarrow \text{MinTheory}((\Gamma_0, \dots, \Gamma_{k-1}), \mathbf{r}[0])$ costs $\mathcal{O}(M \cdot |\mathbf{r}[0]| \cdot \log k)$ by Theorem 3. If $i=k$, the algorithm returns immediately. Otherwise it performs one conjunction $\Gamma_i \cdot \overline{\mathbf{r}[1]}$ (plus a zero test). Using Bryant's bound for apply, this costs $\mathcal{O}(|\Gamma_i| \cdot |\overline{\mathbf{r}[1]}|) \leq \mathcal{O}(M \cdot |\mathbf{r}[1]|)$; the zero test is $\mathcal{O}(1)$. Summing the two contributions yields

$$\mathcal{O}\left(M \cdot (|\mathbf{r}[0]| \cdot \log k + |\mathbf{r}[1]|)\right),$$

which is polynomial in the input sizes. \square

Theorem 6. *Inference is sound and complete for System Z conditional entailment.*

Proof. Assume RationalClosure (RC) is sound and complete for System Z entailment Casini, Meyer, and Varzinczak (2019). We show Inference returns exactly what RC returns on every input $r = \alpha \sim \beta$. (i) Both procedures first find the least rank i where $\Gamma_i \wedge \alpha$ is satisfiable. RC does this via its consistency search; Inference computes $i \leftarrow \text{MinTheory}((\Gamma_0, \dots, \Gamma_{k-1}), \mathbf{r}[0])$, which is the same search expressed as ROBDD zero tests (Theorem 4). Hence the indices coincide, including the case $i=k$ (no α -world). (ii) Given i , RC entails $\alpha \sim \beta$ iff $\Gamma_i \wedge \alpha \wedge \neg\beta$ is unsatisfiable (equivalently, $\Gamma_i \models \alpha \rightarrow \beta$). Inference performs exactly this test as the ROBDD zero test $\Gamma_i \cdot \overline{\mathbf{r}[1]} = 0$, where $\overline{\mathbf{r}[1]}$ encodes $\alpha \wedge \neg\beta$. In the $i=k$ case, both procedures accept r vacuously. Therefore Inference and RC agree on all inputs. By the assumed correctness of RC, Inference is sound and complete. \square

Theorem 7. *The time complexity of the Update algorithm is bounded by $(\Delta' = \Delta \cup \{r\})$*

$$\mathcal{O}\left((|\Gamma| + (m+1) \cdot \max_{\mathbf{r}' \in \Delta'} |\mathbf{r}'[0]|) \cdot \prod_{j=0}^m \max_{\mathbf{r}' \in \Delta'} |\mathbf{r}'[1]|)\right),$$

and requires exponential time in the worst case.

Proof. Let $M_0 = \max_{\mathbf{r}' \in \Delta'} |\mathbf{r}'[0]|$ and $M_1 = \max_{\mathbf{r}' \in \Delta'} |\mathbf{r}'[1]|$. Each loop iteration (i) inserts the current bump set \mathcal{C} into the read-side layer Δ_i , (ii) writes the updated materialised theory

$$\Gamma_{i-v} \leftarrow \left(\prod_{\mathbf{r}' \in \mathcal{C}} \mathbf{r}'[1]\right) \cdot \Gamma_i,$$

and (iii) recomputes the next bump set by testing, for each $\mathbf{r}' \in \Delta_i$, whether $\Gamma_{i-v} \cdot \mathbf{r}'[0] = 0$.

Materialisation cost. By Bryant's bound, a single conjunction costs $\mathcal{O}(|G_1| \cdot |G_2|)$. Upper-bounding each $\mathbf{r}'[1]$ by M_1 and folding the product gives

$$\mathcal{O}\left(|\Gamma_i| \cdot \prod_{\mathbf{r}' \in \mathcal{C}} M_1\right) \leq \mathcal{O}\left(|\Gamma| \cdot \prod_{\ell=0}^t M_1\right),$$

where t counts materialisations accumulated so far. Over the whole run, each rule's materialization appears in the product at most once (when it is first bumped), and in the worst case all $m+1$ rules (including the new one) are bumped. Hence the global materialisation factor is bounded by

$$\mathcal{O}\left(|\Gamma| \cdot \prod_{j=0}^m M_1\right).$$

Antecedent tests. Line 10 performs one conjunction/zero-test per $\mathbf{r}' \in \Delta_i$, each costing $\mathcal{O}(|\Gamma_{i-v}| \cdot |\mathbf{r}'[0]|) \leq \mathcal{O}(|\Gamma_{i-v}| \cdot M_0)$. Each rule can be tested at most once per visited layer; the while-loop advances i monotonically and eliminates fully bumped layers, so across the run there are at most $m+1$ such batches. Thus the total antecedent-testing cost is bounded by

$$\mathcal{O}\left((m+1) \cdot M_0 \cdot \prod_{j=0}^m M_1\right),$$

dominated by the same materialisation product. Combining both contributions yields the stated bound. Worst-case exponential time follows from the fact that unbounded conjunction over many ROBDD operands can cause exponential blow-up Darwiche and Marques (2002). \square

Theorem 8. *Update is sound and complete for single-rule insertion under System Z (partitioning and materialization).*

Proof. Fix $\mathcal{K} = (\Gamma, \Delta)$ with compiled $(\Gamma_0, \dots, \Gamma_{k-1}, \Gamma_\infty)$ and $(\Delta_0, \dots, \Delta_{k-1}, \Delta_\infty)$. Let \mathbf{r} be the inserted rule and set $\Delta' = \Delta \cup \{r\}$. Denote by $(\Gamma'_0, \dots, \Gamma'_{k'-1}, \Gamma'_\infty), (\Delta'_0, \dots, \Delta'_{k'-1}, \Delta'_\infty)$ the outputs of Preprocess on (Γ, Δ') . We show that the results returned by Update coincide. Write $r = (\alpha \sim \beta)$ and let $i^* = \text{MinTheory}((\Gamma_0, \dots, \Gamma_{k-1}), \mathbf{r}[0])$ (line 4). For $j < i^*$, $\Gamma_j \cdot \mathbf{r}[0] = 0$ by definition, hence $\Gamma_j \models \neg\alpha$ and therefore $\Gamma_j \cdot \mathbf{r}[1] = \Gamma_j$ (since $(\neg\alpha \vee \beta)$ is redundant under $\neg\alpha$). Consequently, $\Delta'_j = \Delta_j$ for all $j < i^*$.

Loop invariants. Let the loop variables be i (read index), v (number of vanished layers so far), and \mathcal{C} (current bump set). Define the remainder at read index i by

$$R_i = \mathcal{C} \cup \left(\bigcup_{t \geq i} \Delta_t\right) \cup \Delta_\infty,$$

and the write index by $j = i - v$. We maintain the following invariants at the top of each iteration:

11. *Materialization invariant* $\Gamma_j = \text{ROBDD}\left(\Gamma \wedge \bigwedge_{\mathbf{r}' \in R_i} \mathbf{r}'[1]\right)$.
12. *Remainder/tolerance alignment* For every $\mathbf{r}' \in \Delta_i$, $\Gamma_j \cdot \mathbf{r}'[0] = 0 \iff \mathbf{r}'$ is not tolerated by R_i .
13. *Prefix correctness* The already written layers $(\Delta_0, \dots, \Delta_{j-1})$ and $(\Gamma_0, \dots, \Gamma_{j-1})$ coincide with $(\Delta'_0, \dots, \Delta'_{j-1})$ and $(\Gamma'_0, \dots, \Gamma'_{j-1})$.

Base. Before the first iteration we have $i = i^*, v = 0, \mathcal{C} = \{r\}$ (line 3). By the initial argument, I3 holds up to $j - 1 = i^* - 1$. Line 9 sets $\Gamma_i \leftarrow (\prod_{r' \in \mathcal{C}} r'[1]) \cdot \Gamma_i$, i.e., conjoins $r[1]$ to the old $\Gamma_i = \text{ROBDD}(\Gamma \wedge \bigwedge_{r' \in \mathcal{C}} r'[1])$, yielding I1. Since ROBDD zero tests preserve (un)satisfiability, I2 follows. Thus the invariants hold initially.

Step. Assume I1–I3 at the start of an iteration with read i and write $j = i - v$.

- (A) **Partial bump.** If $|\mathcal{C}| \neq |\Delta_i|$ then line 11 writes survivors $\Delta_j \leftarrow \Delta_i \setminus \mathcal{C}$, where \mathcal{C} was computed at line 10 exactly as the set of non-tolerated rules in Δ_i under remainder R_i (I2). Hence Δ_j is precisely the set of rules tolerated at this stage by Preprocess , i.e., Δ'_j , and the write-side theory Γ_j already equals Γ'_j by I1. Removing the survivors shrinks the remainder to

$$R_{i+1} = \mathcal{C} \cup \left(\bigcup_{t \geq i+1} \Delta_t \right) \cup \Delta_\infty,$$

and line 9 of the *next* iteration will conjoin exactly the materializations of the new \mathcal{C} to form Γ_{j+1} , establishing I1 at the next write index. Thus I3 extends to index j , and I1–I3 are preserved.

- (B) **Vanishing layer (rank increase and write-over).** If $|\mathcal{C}| = |\Delta_i|$, then no rule at the current read layer is tolerated by R_i . In Preprocess , this means the rank produced at this step is empty: $\Delta'_j = \emptyset$, and every rule of Δ_i is carried forward to the next remainder $R_{i+1} = \Delta_i \cup \bigcup_{t \geq i+1} \Delta_t \cup \Delta_\infty$. Equivalently, each such rule's Z-rank strictly increases by at least one (it cannot stay at rank j). Lines 12–15 implement exactly this:

- we increment v , so the write index stays fixed: $j_{\text{next}} = (i+1) - (v+1) = i - v = j$; hence no finite layer is written at j in this iteration (capturing $\Delta'_j = \emptyset$);
- all rules of Δ_i join the carried bump set for the next iteration, so they are re-tested against the next remainder;
- at the start of the next iteration, line 8 inserts the enlarged bump set and line 9 rewrites the same index j , replacing the temporary Γ_j by

$$\Gamma_j \leftarrow \left(\prod_{r' \in \mathcal{C}_{\text{new}}} r'[1] \right) \cdot \Gamma_{i+1},$$

which is precisely the materialized context Preprocess would use at the (conceptual) next rank. Thus the empty rank is skipped and all rules formerly at read layer i are considered at a strictly higher rank, as required.

Hence I1–I3 are preserved.

- (C) **End of finite ranks.** If we reach $i = k-1$ and again $|\mathcal{C}| = |\Delta_i|$, then no rule in \mathcal{C} is ever tolerated; Preprocess consigns them to Δ'_∞ . Lines 16–17 do the same: fold Γ_j into Γ_∞ , move \mathcal{C} to Δ_∞ , then clear \mathcal{C} . This aligns the infinite layer and preserves I3.
- (D) **Early exhaustion ($\mathcal{C} = \emptyset$).** If line 10 yields $\mathcal{C} = \emptyset$ at some read index $i < k-1$, then line 11 writes $\Delta_j = \Delta_i$

(the whole layer survives and, by line 8, already contains r if $i = i^*$), and the loop stops at the next guard. No higher read layer Δ_t with $t \geq i+1$ is modified: the remainder R_{i+1} equals $\bigcup_{t \geq i+1} \Delta_t \cup \Delta_\infty$ (since no rule was bumped at i), so Preprocess would produce the same higher layers, merely shifted down by the accumulated v . The algorithm implements this by returning the written prefix concatenated with the untouched suffix with index shift (see the final `Return`):

$$\begin{aligned} &(\Gamma_0, \dots, \Gamma_{i-v-1}) \parallel (\Gamma_i, \dots, \Gamma_{k+v-1}), \\ &(\Delta_0, \dots, \Delta_{i-v-1}) \parallel (\Delta_i, \dots, \Delta_{k+v-1}). \end{aligned}$$

If $i^* = k$ initially, Preprocess would start the next iteration on the remainder Δ_∞ with materialized theory $\text{ROBDD}(\Gamma \wedge \bigwedge \Delta_\infty[1])$. Lines 6–7 construct exactly this fresh read layer: $\Gamma_k \leftarrow \Gamma \cdot \Gamma_\infty$, $\Delta_k \leftarrow \emptyset$, $k \leftarrow k + 1$. The loop then proceeds as in (A)–(D) with the same invariants. Each iteration strictly increases i ; each rule enters \mathcal{C} at most once; hence the loop terminates. The final $k \leftarrow k - v$ compresses exactly the v vanished layers. If termination occurs by (C), we have processed all finite ranks and matched Preprocess layer-for-layer. If it occurs by (D) with $\mathcal{C} = \emptyset$ at read i , the algorithm returns the concatenation of the already written prefix $0..(i-v-1)$ with the untouched suffix $i..(k+v-1)$, yielding a contiguous partition of length $k-v$; this suffix equals what Preprocess would produce from the same remainder.

$$\begin{aligned} &(\Gamma_0, \dots, \Gamma_{k-1}, \Gamma_\infty) = (\Gamma'_0, \dots, \Gamma'_{k-1}, \Gamma'_\infty), \\ &(\Delta_0, \dots, \Delta_{k-1}, \Delta_\infty) = (\Delta'_0, \dots, \Delta'_{k-1}, \Delta'_\infty). \end{aligned}$$

`Update` returns exactly the Z-partitioning and materialized theories that Preprocess would compute on $(\Gamma, \Delta \cup \{r\})$. Combined with Theorem 2, this proves soundness and completeness for single-rule insertion. \square

Theorem 9. *The time complexity of the procedure described by Equation 1 is bounded by*

$$\mathcal{O}\left(\prod_{i=0}^{k-1} |\Gamma_i|\right),$$

and requires exponential time in the worst case.

Proof. Let $A_i = \text{ITE}(\Gamma_i, i, \infty)$ for $i = 0, \dots, k-1$. Constructing A_i from Γ_i requires a single linear traversal of Γ_i , hence $\mathcal{O}(|\Gamma_i|)$ time. The final ADD is $A_0 \cdot A_1 \cdot \dots \cdot A_{k-1}$, implemented by folding apply. For two ADDs G_1, G_2 , apply runs in $\mathcal{O}(|G_1| \cdot |G_2|)$. If we fold left, the t -th combination costs $\mathcal{O}(|A_0 \cdot \dots \cdot A_{t-1}| \cdot |A_t|) \leq \mathcal{O}(\prod_{i=0}^t |A_i|)$. Summing over t yields the bound $\mathcal{O}(\prod_{i=0}^{k-1} |A_i|)$, and since $|A_i| = \mathcal{O}(|\Gamma_i|)$ we obtain $\mathcal{O}(\prod_{i=0}^{k-1} |\Gamma_i|)$. ROBDD/ADD compilation can be exponential in the input size, so the overall procedure is exponential in the worst case. \square

Theorem 10. *Equation 1 is sound and complete for compiling the ADD representation $\kappa_{\mathcal{K}}^Z$ of the ranking function $\kappa_{\mathcal{K}}^Z$.*

Proof. Recall from proof of Theorem 4 that for any ω ,

$$\kappa_{\mathcal{K}}^Z(\omega) = \min\{i \mid \omega \models \Gamma_i\},$$

and $\kappa_{\mathcal{K}}^Z(\omega) = \infty$ if $\omega \not\models \Gamma$. For each i , $\mathbf{A}_i = \text{ITE}(\Gamma_i, i, \infty)$ evaluates to i on worlds satisfying Γ_i and to ∞ otherwise. Therefore, for every world ω the pointwise minimum

$$\left(\prod_{i=0}^{k-1} \mathbf{A}_i\right)(\omega) = \min\{i \mid \omega \models \Gamma_i\}$$

This matches exactly the definition of $\kappa_{\mathcal{K}}^Z$. Hence the ADD produced by Equation 1 computes $\kappa_{\mathcal{K}}^Z$ on all worlds; equivalently, the compilation is both sound (no wrong values) and complete (all values defined). \square

Theorem 11. *The conditioning operator given in Equation 2 can be computed with a worst-case running time*

$$\mathcal{O}(|\varphi| \cdot |\kappa|^2),$$

and therefore runs in polynomial time in the sizes of the input diagrams.

Proof. Let $n_\varphi = |\varphi|$ and $n_\kappa = |\kappa|$. We analyse the construction from Equation 2 in terms of standard ADD/ROBDD primitives.

Step 1: restrict κ to φ and $\neg\varphi$. We first form the guarded diagrams

$$\mathbf{A}_\varphi = \text{ITE}(\varphi, \kappa, \infty), \quad \mathbf{A}_{\neg\varphi} = \text{ITE}(\overline{\varphi}, \kappa, \infty).$$

By the standard complexity bound for ITE each call runs in time

$$\mathcal{O}(n_\varphi \cdot n_\kappa)$$

and produces a diagram of size $\mathcal{O}(n_\varphi \cdot n_\kappa)$ in the worst case.

Step 2: compute the offsets. The offsets

$$k_\varphi = \min(\mathbf{A}_\varphi), \quad k_{\neg\varphi} = \min(\mathbf{A}_{\neg\varphi})$$

are obtained by a linear traversal of \mathbf{A}_φ and $\mathbf{A}_{\neg\varphi}$, respectively. Each traversal visits every node at most once, hence both minima can be computed in time

$$\mathcal{O}(|\mathbf{A}_\varphi|) + \mathcal{O}(|\mathbf{A}_{\neg\varphi}|)$$

in the worst case.

Step 3: shift the ranking diagram. We now construct the shifted copies

$$\kappa_1 = \kappa - k_\varphi, \quad \kappa_2 = \kappa - k_{\neg\varphi} + m.$$

This costs $\mathcal{O}(n_\kappa)$ per shift, so overall $\mathcal{O}(n_\kappa)$ for both, and the sizes of κ_1 and κ_2 remain $\mathcal{O}(n_\kappa)$.

Step 4: assemble the conditioned ranking. Finally, Equation 2 defines

$$\kappa_{[\varphi, m]} = \text{ITE}(\varphi, \kappa_1, \kappa_2).$$

This is a single ITE call with guard of size n_φ and branches of size $\mathcal{O}(n_\kappa)$ each, so by the same complexity bound as above its runtime is

$$\mathcal{O}(n_\varphi \cdot n_\kappa^2)$$

and the resulting ADD has worst-case size $\mathcal{O}(n_\varphi \cdot n_\kappa^2)$.

Collecting the costs, we perform a constant number of ITE calls on inputs of sizes n_φ and n_κ , plus a constant number of linear traversals. Thus the overall time complexity is

$$\mathcal{O}(n_\varphi \cdot n_\kappa^2),$$

which is polynomial in the sizes of the input diagrams, as claimed. \square

Theorem 12. *Equation 2 is sound/complete for Spohn conditioning.*

Proof. We work pointwise over worlds ω . By definition,

$$k_\varphi = \min(\text{ITE}(\varphi, \kappa, \infty)) = \min\{\kappa(\omega) \mid \omega \models \varphi\} = \kappa(\varphi),$$

with $\min \emptyset = \infty$ when φ is unsatisfiable, and similarly $k_{\neg\varphi} = \kappa(\neg\varphi)$.

Now take an arbitrary ω . If $\omega \models \varphi$, then by the semantics of ITE,

$$\kappa_{[\varphi, m]}(\omega) = (\kappa - k_\varphi)(\omega) = \kappa(\omega) - \kappa(\varphi),$$

which matches the definition of Spohn conditioning. If $\omega \models \neg\varphi$, we instead obtain

$$\kappa_{[\varphi, m]}(\omega) = (\kappa - k_{\neg\varphi} + m)(\omega) = \kappa(\omega) - \kappa(\neg\varphi) + m,$$

again exactly the desired value.

For worlds ω with $\kappa(\omega) = \infty$ (impossible worlds), both branches evaluate to ∞ by absorption, and if φ or $\neg\varphi$ is unsatisfiable, the corresponding offset is ∞ and that branch is never selected. Hence Equation 2 agrees with $\kappa_{[\varphi, m]}$ on all ω , which establishes soundness and completeness. \square

Theorem 13. *The time complexity of the entailment test in Equation 3, applied to a compiled conditional \mathbf{r} , is bounded by*

$$\mathcal{O}(|\kappa| \cdot |\mathbf{r}[0]| \cdot |\mathbf{r}[1]|),$$

and is polynomial in the sizes of κ and \mathbf{r} in the worst case.

Proof. The test performs a constant number of decision-diagram operations:

- It builds the Boolean mask for $\alpha \wedge \beta$ as $\mathbf{r}[0] \cdot \mathbf{r}[1]$, which costs $\mathcal{O}(|\mathbf{r}[0]| \cdot |\mathbf{r}[1]|)$ by the standard apply bound.
- It then constructs the $\alpha \wedge \beta$ branch as $\text{ITE}(\mathbf{r}[0] \cdot \mathbf{r}[1], \kappa, \infty)$, which costs $\mathcal{O}(|\kappa| \cdot |\mathbf{r}[0]| \cdot |\mathbf{r}[1]|)$ and bounds the size of the resulting ADD.
- For the $\alpha \wedge \neg\beta$ branch it forms $\overline{\mathbf{r}[1]}$, which is $\mathcal{O}(1)$ with complemented edges and has size $|\mathbf{r}[1]|$, and then constructs $\text{ITE}(\overline{\mathbf{r}[1]}, \kappa, \infty)$ in $\mathcal{O}(|\kappa| \cdot |\mathbf{r}[1]|)$.
- Finally, it computes the minima of the two resulting ADDs, each by a single traversal, so in time linear in their sizes.

The dominating term is the call $\text{ITE}(\mathbf{r}[0] \cdot \mathbf{r}[1], \kappa, \infty)$, which yields an overall running time in

$$\mathcal{O}(|\kappa| \cdot |\mathbf{r}[0]| \cdot |\mathbf{r}[1]|),$$

which is clearly polynomial in the sizes of κ and \mathbf{r} . \square

Theorem 14 (ADD entailment). *Equation 3 is sound/complete for System Z entailment.*

Proof. Let $r = \alpha \sim \beta$. For a formula φ , define

$$\kappa(\varphi) = \min\{\kappa(\omega) \mid \omega \models \varphi\},$$

with $\kappa(\varphi) = \infty$ if φ has no models. By definition of masking, the ADD

$$\text{ITE}(\varphi, \kappa, \infty)$$

satisfies

$$(\text{ITE}(\varphi, \kappa, \infty))(\omega) = \begin{cases} \kappa(\omega), & \omega \models \varphi, \\ \infty, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

so $\min(\text{ITE}(\varphi, \kappa, \infty)) = \kappa(\varphi)$.

Applying this to the masks for $\alpha \wedge \beta$ and $\alpha \wedge \neg\beta$ gives

$$\min(\text{ITE}(\alpha \cdot \beta, \kappa, \infty)) = \kappa(\alpha \wedge \beta),$$

$$\min(\text{ITE}(\alpha \cdot \bar{\beta}, \kappa, \infty)) = \kappa(\alpha \wedge \neg\beta).$$

In the non-vacuous case, where some α -worlds exist, the ranking-based semantics accepts r iff

$$\kappa(\alpha \wedge \beta) < \kappa(\alpha \wedge \neg\beta),$$

which is exactly the inequality tested in Equation 3. In the vacuous case, where α has no models, both minima are ∞ , and the separate check $\min(\text{ITE}(\alpha, \kappa, \infty)) = \infty$ correctly identifies r as vacuously accepted under the standard convention. Hence the procedure (vacuity check plus inequality) is sound and complete for defeasible entailment with respect to κ . \square

3 Supplementary Material C: Extended Experimental Results

The main total preprocessing results for the SAT pipeline include both CNF conversion (for the antecedent and consequent of every conditional) and the total time required to run the preprocessing algorithm. Table 1 summarizes the time required for each.

N	Total preprocessing (μs)	
	CNF Conversion	Preprocessing
6	51.3	238.8
8	75.6	387.9
10	96.1	573.0
12	111.7	739.6
14	125.1	952.8
16	144.9	1166.6
18	156.3	1413.2
20	165.6	1629.7
30	236.2	3315.0
40	312.4	5422.2
M1	86.9	710.2
M2	100.7	1377.6

Table 1: SAT pipeline: CNF conversion and preprocessing.

We note that while CNF conversion adds a noticeable increase in runtime, the total runtime is still dominated by the

preprocessing step, as expected. The main ROBDD preprocessing results include the time required to compile each conditional in the knowledge base into its ROBDD encoding, the total time to run the preprocessing algorithm, and the total time spent on a single dynamic variable ordering pass using the basic sifting algorithm Rudell (1993), after which further reordering was locked for the subsequent inference and update procedures. Table 2 summarizes the time required for each.

N	Total preprocessing (μs)		
	Compilation	Preprocessing	DVR
6	190.3	9.9	364.0
8	280.0	18.6	405.2
10	280.9	41.3	480.7
12	264.5	57.0	554.2
14	286.3	92.7	656.3
16	284.6	146.4	820.2
18	369.3	219.6	1028.2
20	274.6	286.2	1254.2
30	377.7	4487.6	5984.8
40	427.9	87867.4	55310.9
M1	102.6	39.8	730.9
M2	306.9	620.1	3527.1

Table 2: ROBDD pipeline: compilation, preprocessing, and DVR.

We note that the compilation time does not increase substantially, likely because the initial compilation step compiles each conditional separately without performing full materialization (i.e., combining conditionals). We also note that the overall runtime is dominated by dynamic variable reordering, which aligns with expectations, as DVR is typically computationally expensive.

Finally, we include two ablation tables illustrating the difference in ROBDD and ADD inference with and without applying DVR after the initial preprocessing algorithm. Table 3 presents the results for ROBDD inference, while Table 4 presents the results for ADD inference. The results show a consistent speedup ranging from 1.5 to 3.3 for ROBDD inference and from 1.3 to 6 for ADD inference. The larger benefit for ADD inference is expected due to its greater sensitivity to variable ordering, which arises from the additional terminal nodes used to encode the ranks.

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N	ROBDD Inference (μs)		
	DVR	NODVR	NODVR/DVR
6	2.0	3.0	1.5
8	2.9	4.3	1.5
10	3.6	6.0	1.6
12	4.7	7.0	1.5
14	5.8	9.5	1.6
16	8.0	14.0	1.8
18	10.3	20.0	2.0
20	12.1	26.4	2.2
30	87.2	286.1	3.3
40	701.4	2029.4	2.9
M1	5.3	5.8	1.1
M2	21.3	27.1	1.3

Table 3: Average ROBDD inference time with and without dynamic variable reordering (DVR).

N	ADD Inference (μs)		
	DVR	NODVR	NODVR/DVR
6	3.5	4.7	1.3
8	5.4	7.4	1.4
10	7.3	10.9	1.5
12	9.4	14.5	1.5
14	11.5	20.1	1.8
16	15.1	30.2	2.0
18	20.9	46.4	2.2
20	22.8	55.6	2.4
30	111.6	489.4	4.4
40	775.3	4667.6	6.0
M1	10.6	9.7	0.9
M2	14.2	40.1	2.8

Table 4: Average ADD inference time with and without dynamic variable reordering (DVR).

Rudell, R. 1993. Dynamic variable ordering for ordered binary decision diagrams. In *Proceedings of 1993 International Conference on Computer Aided Design (ICCAD)*, 42–47.